

ACOUSTIC BAND GAPS IN SONIC CRYSTAL COMPOSITES FOR AUDIBLE FREQUENCY NOISE REDUCTION

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SUMMARY: Audible noise from machinery and other sources can be not only annoying but also a health hazard to personnel nearby. This noise is generally band limited in a certain frequency range and should be abated. Commercially available sound absorbing materials attenuate sound over a broad frequency band; but the attenuation may not be sufficient in the desired frequency band. We are fabricating and characterizing geometrically compact composites called sonic crystals for shielding against noise generally limited to a particular frequency band. These composites have periodic arrays of macroscopic acoustic scatterers arranged in a pattern analogous to a single crystal lattice in a host matrix material. The solid scatterers of relatively high acoustic impedance are imbedded in a host matrix material of low acoustic impedance or *vice versa*. We have demonstrated that in these composites, the sound transmission for certain frequencies drops abruptly, giving rise to frequency band gaps. In this paper we discuss propagation of audible white noise in sonic crystals. We demonstrate that the sonic crystal attenuates certain frequencies in the transmission of audible noise drastically. The attenuation in transmission, bandwidth and the location of the “forbidden” frequency band (also known as acoustic band gap) depends upon the characteristics such as material properties and crystal lattice properties of the sonic crystal. In order to measure acoustic band gaps in these acoustic-damping materials, an audio loudspeaker directs sound consisting of white noise at the sonic crystal specimen placed in a reflection less acoustic enclosure. A wide band microphone measures the transmitted sound amplitude; fast Fourier transformed and normalized to obtain normalized transmission spectra. The reduction in transmitted sound amplitude in the band gaps depends upon the material properties of scatterers and host, fill ratio and lattice configuration. We present detailed results for acoustic band gaps in the propagation of sound waves through several macroscopic sonic crystals with various types of scatterers and explore their industrial uses for noise reduction.

KEYWORDS: Sonic crystals, acoustic band gaps, audible noise.

INTRODUCTION

Sonic crystal composites [1-3] are geometrically engineered materials made from periodic arrays of scatterers embedded in a host material. Scatterers can be solid or fluid imbedded in a host material which can be fluid or a solid such as unsaturated polyester resins, epoxy etc. These binary inhomogeneous materials behave like crystals. When sound is incident on the face of such crystals, the transmission amplitude is reduced drastically for a band of frequencies, giving rise to acoustic band gaps. The amplitude of transmitted sound in the band gaps, width of the band gap and its location depends upon the periodic geometrical arrangement (crystallographic lattice), lattice constants, material properties such as mass density, elastic modulus, shear modulus and acoustic impedances of the scatterers and the matrix material. The gap characteristics also depend on the direction of propagation of sound, i.e., wave vector with respect to crystallographic axis, fill factors, FF (in 3-D, FF is defined as volume fraction of scatterers

in a unit cell and in 2-D, it is defined as the cross sectional area of scatterers in a unit cell of the host material) and the shape of scatterers.

Most of the work done on acoustic band gaps has been on propagation of sound *pulse* in sonic crystals, using acrylic cylinders arranged in air in a square pattern [4,5], close-packed array of polymer tubes containing water arranged on a honeycomb lattice in air [6], periodic array of air cylinders in water [7], square array of copper cylinders in air [8]. Batra et al [9] showed existence of acoustic bands, in sonic crystals composed of hollow beads and lead spheres arranged in 3-D cubic array and cast in resin, using *continuous sound waves*. Very little work has been done on *propagation of audible noise* in sonic crystals. In this paper, we present propagation of audible noise in sonic crystals composed of cylindrical rods of different materials arranged in a square array in air. We present experimental results for propagation of white noise in these crystals for different FF by rearranging the rods and/or direction of propagation of sound in the sonic crystal. Finally, we demonstrate the utility such a sonic crystals in suppression of band limited audible noise from an industrial noise source.

EXPERIMENTAL

Specimens:

We fabricated several specimens of sonic crystals by using commercially available acrylic rods, rubber shrink tubes and stainless steel tubes to study their characteristics for noise suppression. The types of materials used are available in a wide variety of sizes, providing flexibility in design of sonic crystals for specific applications. We fabricated 2-D sonic crystals using solid cylindrical acrylic rod scatterers arranged periodically in an 8x8 square array in matrix material air. Figure 1 shows these sonic crystal specimens composed of acrylic rods. Each rod of length 15.3 cm and diameter 0.95 cm is held in position

Fig.1 Sonic crystals composed of acrylic rods arranged periodically in a square array in host material air. Each rod, of length 15.3 cm and diameter 0.95 cm, held in position in a plastic grid with a lattice constant ~ 2.54 cm. The configurations are: (A) Square array of acrylic rods with $FF = 0.11$; (B) Square array of rubber shrink tube encased acrylic rods with a $FF = 0.12$; (C) Face centered square array of acrylic rods with a $FF = 0.22$.

in a square grid with a lattice constant ~ 2.54 cm. The geometrical configurations are (a) square array of acrylic rods (b) square array of rubber shrink tube (of thickness 0.05 cm.) encased acrylic rods and (c) face centered square array of acrylic rods. Figure 2 shows square array (8x8) of steel pipes; each pipe has length of 15.3 cm, OD = 0.95 cm and ID = 0.64 cm. The lattice constant for sonic crystal shown in Figs 2A and 2B are ~ 2.54 cm 1.27 cm respectively. We varied the geometric arrangement of the rods to allow sound propagation parallel to the square edges, i.e., along [100] or along the diagonal direction i.e., along [110] of the crystal. Finally, we fabricated a specimen using stainless tube and rubber encased acrylic rods arranged alternatively in a square lattice with lattice constant of 1.27cm.

Measurement of Acoustic Band Gaps

Figure 3 shows the experimental arrangement used for measurement of acoustic band gaps. We performed experiments to measure the frequency band gaps in acoustic transmission spectra through each of the above specimens. An amplified white noise signal (Fig.4) from a function generator is used to excite a loudspeaker mounted one side of a reflection less acoustic enclosure (Fig.3). The audible noise from the loudspeaker is projected through a hole into the enclosure and is incident upon the face of the specimen placed in the enclosure. The sound transmitted through the specimen is received at the opposite parallel face by a small microphone and amplified. The amplitude of the transmitted sound is signal processed and measured by a digital signal analyzer (DSA) as a function of frequency. The digitized data is saved in a file for further analysis. The transmitted sound signal spectrum is normalized to the transmission amplitude in air. Data is analyzed to determine acoustic band gaps and the corresponding reduction in noise in such frequency bands.

Fig.2. Two-dimensional sonic crystals with different lattice properties. (A) Stainless steel pipes arranged in an 8x8 square array in air. Each pipe has length = 15.3 cm, OD = 0.95 cm and ID = 0.64 cm. The lattice constant is ~ 2.54 cm and FF = 0.06; (B) Square array in Fig. 2A rearranged in a square lattice with lattice constant of 1.27 cm, giving FF = 0.25 for [100] and 0.49 for [110] directions of propagation. (C) Square array of rubber shrink tube encased acrylic rods with lattice constant of 1.27 cm, giving FF of 0.25 for [100] and 0.49 for [110] directions of propagation; (D) Square array of steel tubes and rubber shrink tube encased acrylic rods with lattice constant of 1.27 cm, giving FF = 0.25 for [100] and 0.49 for [110] directions of propagation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Before presenting our experimental results, we discuss briefly the origin of acoustic band gaps. A sonic crystal can be represented by a set of parallel planes of acoustic scatterers. Any sound wave incident on these planes is reflected back from each of such planes due to acoustic impedance mismatch. According to Bragg law, when a monochromatic wave is incident on the surface of a crystal, condition for back diffraction is given by the following equation

$$2 d \sin \theta = n \lambda \quad (1)$$

where d is the lattice constant, θ is the angle of incident with respect to plane of scatterers, λ is the wavelength of the incident beam and n is an integer 1,2, etc.. Assuming sound beam is collimated and incident at $\theta = 90^\circ$, (since $\lambda = c/f$ where c is the sound velocity in the host material (air) and f is the frequency of sound wave) we obtain frequencies

$$f_n = n c / 2 d \quad (2)$$

for which the back scattering is maximum. This implies that for such frequencies, the transmitted sound wave is minimum. If the incident sound beam is white noise, the back scattering will be maximum only for those frequencies for which condition (2) is satisfied. In other words, for such frequencies, the sonic crystal will allow minimum transmission of sound, thus giving rise to acoustic band gaps in the transmission amplitude. This explains, in very simple terms, the existence of acoustic band gaps in the transmission of sound in sonic crystal. Due to this characteristic, sonic crystals can act as a passive filters for band of frequencies in the acoustic band gap. We will illustrate this inference later in this section.

We now present the results for transmission of white noise sound signal through the sonic crystals specimens discussed in the previous section. Figure 4 shows the white noise sound signal incident on the sonic crystal specimen placed inside the reflection less sound enclosure. The normalized transmission amplitude spectra for noise incident on a square array sonic crystal shown in Fig.1 are shown in Fig. 5. According to Bragg law, since these specimens have the same lattices (square array) and lattice constants (2.54 cm.), the acoustic bands in the transmission should occur between the same frequencies. This explains the overlap of transmission spectra for cases (a), (b) and (c) in Fig. 5A. However, the FF, in the direction of sound propagation, is different for each these three specimens. For square array of acrylic rods specimen (Fig.1A), FF is 0.11; for square array of shrink tube encased acrylic rods, FF is 0.12 (Fig.1B) and for face center array (Fig.1C), FF is almost twice i.e., 0.22. We compare normalized transmission amplitude as a function of FF in these sonic crystals in Fig. 5A. Though the pattern of sound transmission spectra is similar for all three cases, the magnitude of normalized transmission amplitude is different. The suppression of noise is more pronounced for the cases (b) and (c); former due to rubber tube encasing of the scatterers and latter due to higher fill ratio of the scatterers. The dotted curve (-----) “a” represents transmission spectra of white noise for propagation along [100] in the square array (Fig. 1A). Since FF is very low for this specimen, the dominant acoustic band gap between 12.7 and 22.3 kHz is not well defined. However, when the rods are encased with rubber shrink tube, the depth of the acoustic band.

Fig.3. Diagram of experimental setup. The size of the enclosure is 2ftx1ftx1ft and is lined with 2” thick convoluted urethane foam. The shape of the foam increases absorptive surface area and reduces the reverberations.

Fig.4. Incident white noise sound signal.

gap increases as shown by the bold dotted line (-----) in curve “b”. When the sound noise signal is propagated along [110], the FF is increased to 0.22 and we observe deeper acoustic band gap between 5.3 and 8.0 kHz with maximum attenuation of ~ 17 dB and between 12.7 kHz, 22.3 kHz with maximum attenuation of ~ 20 dB. Since the raw data has lot of scatter, it is hard to pinpoint start and end frequencies for the acoustic band gap. Digital signal processing of the raw data shown in Fig.5A reduces the scatter in the data as shown in Fig.5B. For example, the wide acoustic band gap between 11.0 and 21.8 kHz with maximum attenuation of ~ 12.4 dB both for rubber encased acrylic rods for propagation along [100]) and for acrylic rods specimen when propagation is along [110] are clearer. Comparing curves (b) and (c) in Fig. 5B, we observe that encasing of the rods with rubber in a sonic crystal with low FF can achieve almost the same attenuation in the band gap (~ 12.4 dB) as the crystal with higher FF.

Fig.5. Frequency dependence of transmission coefficient of white noise sound propagated through sonic crystals of square array (8x8) of acrylic rods. Fig.5A shows transmission data for propagation of white noise sound signal (a) along [100] in the square array of acrylic rods with FF = 0.11; (b) along [100] in the square array of rubber encased acrylic rods with FF = 0.12; (c) along [110] in the square array of acrylic rods with FF = 0.22.

Fig.6. Frequency dependence of transmission coefficient of sound propagated through sonic crystals of square array (8x8) of steel pipes. Fig.6A shows raw data for normalized transmission amplitude for propagation of white noise sound signal (a) along [100] in specimen shown in Fig. 2A with a FF = 0.06; (b) along [100] in specimen shown in Fig.2B, with a FF = 0.25; (c) along [110] for specimen shown in Fig.2B, with FF = 0.49. Fig. 6B shows signal processed data shown in Fig. 6A.

We also studied the acoustic bands of sonic crystal specimens composed of square array of steel tubes as shown in Fig.2A and 2B. Curve (a) in Fig.6A gives the spectrum of normalized transmission amplitude for propagation of noise along [100] in such a specimen with lattice constant of 2.54 cm and FF of 0.06. As the FF is increased to 0.25 by decreasing the lattice constant to one half, i.e., 1.27 cm, the dominant acoustic band between 11.0 kHz and 20.8 kHz becomes more pronounced as shown by curve (b) in Fig.6A. Propagation along [110] for specimen used for curve (b) increases the FF to 0.49, making the onset of acoustic band gap at 11.0 kHz sharper as shown by curve (c) in Fig.6A. The maximum drop in amplitude of transmitted noise is ~ 12 dB in this acoustic band gap. Signal processing removes the scatter in the data shown in Fig.6A and corresponding curves are shown in Fig.6B. Signal processing facilitates identification of the acoustic bands in the data, however, it reduces the value of measured attenuation in the acoustic band between 11.0 and 20.8 kHz. Similar results were obtained for specimens shown in Figs. 2C and 2D.

The sonic crystals, due to their characteristics of producing large attenuation in a selective frequency range due to acoustic band gaps, can be used as passive filters for band limited noise in the audible frequency range. Many machinery produce noise, which is generally limited to a frequency band, characteristic of the machine. We used noise from an industrial vacuum cleaner to demonstrate band limited filtering properties of some of the sonic crystals. The experimental set up is shown in Fig.7A. The vacuum cleaner was placed about 2 feet away from the microphone. The noise generated by the vacuum cleaner occurs in the frequency band between 0.15 kHz and 2.0 kHz as shown by curve (b) in Fig. 7B. According to Bragg's law, none of the sonic crystals of reasonable size could produce acoustic band gaps in this frequency range. Liu et al [10,11] reported occurrence of frequency bands for frequencies less than 2 kHz, in a sonic crystal composed of rubber coated lead spheres of diameter of 1.00 cm arranged in a 8x8x8 cubic array with a lattice constant of 1.55 cm and cast in epoxy as a hard matrix material. Such a crystal produces acoustic band gaps in frequency range less than 2 kHz and phenomena is attributed to local resonances set up in the rubber coated lead spheres cast periodically in epoxy. Following their

approach, we fabricated a similar but simpler sonic crystal (shown in Fig. 2C) composed of square array (8x8) of rubber shrink tube encased acrylic rods of diameter 0.95 cm. with lattice constant of 1.27 cm, giving FF of 0.49 for propagation along [110]. The transmission amplitude spectrum of white noise for this sonic crystal in the frequency range below 2.5 kHz is shown by curve (a) in Fig. 7B. After recording the noise from the vacuum cleaner and without disturbing the position of the microphone, the above sonic crystal was placed as an intervening medium between the microphone and vacuum cleaner. This resulting frequency content and amplitude of the noise passing through the crystal was recorded and is displayed by curve (c) in Fig.7B. It shows that the amplitude characteristic noise peaks (ii) between 1.4kHz and 1.7 kHz has been filtered out by the acoustic band gap between 1.3 kHz and 1.8 kHz. Its amplitude drops from -24.7 dBm to -37.8 dBm, giving an attenuation of almost 13 dB. It is hard to explain similar results for filtering below 0.4 kHz due to lack to reliable sonic crystal data due to insensitivity of the loudspeaker used for generating white noise for curve (a) in Fig.7B, at such low frequencies. Nonetheless, these results demonstrate potential use of sonic crystals for abatement of frequency-limited noise.

Fig. 7. (A) Experimental arrangement to demonstrate suppression of noise by a sonic crystal. (B) Results of demonstration using a sonic crystal fabricated using a square array of rubber shrink tube encased acrylic rods with lattice constant of 1.27 cm shown in Fig. 2C. Microphone is aligned to receive optimum transmitted signal along the diagonal direction (FF=0.49). Curves shown in Fig. 7B are:(a) zoomed spectra for white noise transmitted through sonic crystal; (b) Spectra of noise from an industrial vacuum cleaner; (c) spectra of vacuum cleaner noise transmitted through the sonic crystal. Notice the selective filtering action of the sonic crystal.

Sonic crystals discussed above are made of rods or tubes and have open periodic structure. They have potential use for abatement of noise from the highways passing through residential communities. The rod material, lattice structure and lattice constants can be chosen properly to have full band gaps in the desired range of frequencies present in the noise.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented results for sonic crystals made of periodic array of solid scatterers. The scatterers used were solid acrylic rods and stainless tubes arranged in an 8x8 square array in air. These sonic crystals show acoustic band gaps in the transmission of white noise sound. The acoustic band gaps depend on material properties of the scatterers, direction of propagation and fill ratio. The complexity of transmission amplitude of sound could be due to lack of *perfect* periodic arrangement. The slight disagreement of experimental results from Bragg's law predictions could be due to lack of collimated beam from the loudspeaker, resulting in sound beam incident at angles other than 90° as was assumed. We also demonstrated the selective filtering properties of these sonic crystals in abatement of band-limited noise from an industrial vacuum cleaner.

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